

Exploring Autonomy And Identity: Existential Crisis In R. K. Narayan's *The Dark Room*

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Abstract: This paper critically examines the identity and existential crisis of women by observing the life of the female protagonist in R. K. Narayan's 1938 novel *The Dark Room*. It will focus on the traditional role of women in Indian society. It will also focus on the traditional values and norms which embrace superstition and conservative thought by offering superiority to men. Hence, this paper especially focuses on the oppression of women in a patriarchal society in which women are marginalised, subjugated and confined within household activities which is the reality of a traditional patriarchal society. *The Dark Room* explores the lives of its characters in a deeply reflective way, which, combined with themes of gender and power dynamics, opens up interesting avenues for examining existential crises and feminist issues. The novel is centred on the life of Savitri, a middle-class woman in colonial-era India, whose existence revolves around her children and her oppressive marriage to her husband, Ramani.

Keywords: Alienation, Autonomy, Duality, Existential Crisis, Psychological Torment, Search for Identity.

Rasipuram Krishnaswami Iyer Narayanaswami (1906–2001) is among the best-known and most widely read Indian authors writing his novels in the English language. He was among the leading authors of early Indian literature in English along with Mulk Raj Anand and Raja Rao. Narayan's mentor and friend Graham Greene was influential in getting Narayan's first four books published including his semi-autobiographical trilogy that includes *Swami and Friends* (1935), *The Bachelor of Arts* (1937) and *The English Teacher* (1945). The central character of R.K. Narayan's *The Dark Room* is Savitri, a submissive housewife, very much dominated and neglected by her husband Ramani. There is a dark room in their house where Savitri retreats whenever her husband's harshness seems unbearable to her. But when Ramani starts an affair with the newly appointed Shanta Bai in his office, Savitri leaves her husband's house after a bitter quarrel. She tries unsuccessfully to commit suicide by drowning herself in a river. After some twists, typical of Narayan's style, such as taking up a caretaker's job in an old temple, Savitri cannot bear living without her children and returns home, deciding to live with the burden of her husband having an affair.

Narayan's *The Dark Room* (1938) is a novel that deals with personal and social struggles, especially those experienced by the protagonist Savitri. The story of Savitri's emotional and psychological anguish is inseparably knitted into issues of identity, gender, and existential questioning. Exploring the intersection of existential crisis and feminism in *The Dark Room* can lead to an understanding of how Narayan critiques societal norms in general and specific to the status of women in particular, as well as how Savitri's crisis might echo larger philosophical issues. Existential crisis questions one's place in the world, facing absurdity or meaninglessness concerning one's existence, and wrestling between personal desires and societal expectation. In *The Dark Room*, Savitri undergoes an existential crisis due to complex emotional turbulence after infidelity by her husband Ramani. The novel concerns itself not only with a woman confronting disillusionment but also with the larger issue of human beings who certainly testify to it as themes of suffering, isolation, and quest for meaning in an indifferent world. Savitri's self-worth relies on her function as a wife and mother. The moment she hears about her husband's betrayal, it feels as though she is rejected not only by him but by

the entire structure of her existence. Ramani, an indifferent and selfish character, fulfils neither the emotional nor the existential validation she attempts to create for herself. The existence fractures and it moves back within the “dark room” – a metaphorical and literal space of isolation and contemplation. In the dark room, Savitri reflects upon the emptiness of her marriage and her role as a woman in a patriarchal society. The dark room becomes both a literal space of emotional withdrawal and a symbol of existential despair, where Savitri confronts the absurdity of her existence, her gendered limitations, and her inability to change her circumstances. Narayan uses the dark room of Savitri to portray the condition of many women in their unexpressed existence in a society where roles are predetermined. Savitri’s crisis is not only marital betrayal, but most importantly, a broader realisation of her powerlessness and restricted agency, as well as the apparent meaninglessness of her mundane life. It symbolizes darkness born out of finding no better meaning in life within the given conditions of a wife’s and mother’s duty.

The Dark Room by R.K. Narayan sets itself as a fundamental work in Indian Literature in English and is remarkable for its depiction of traditional South Indian society. The novel follows the life of its female protagonist, Savitri, who embodies the struggle faced by the women in their married life and illuminates the complexities of female existence positioning her existential crisis against the expectations dictated by a culture dominated by men. The character of Savitri acts as an archetype of the woman captured between family duties and personal desires. The concept of the dark room works as a powerful metaphor inside the narrative encapsulating the internal struggle of Savitri. The representation by Narayan of Savitri’s retreat in the dark room represents a submission. The existential questions that arise in these moments of solitude underline its comparison with the social norms that dictate her identity in society. Furthermore, the juxtaposition of Savitri’s retreat in the dark room and the moments of rebellion illustrates the tension between her individual and societal identity. Narayan exposes the duality of Savitri’s existence: while craving for freedom and individual identity she is chained to her duties as a housewife and mother.

In the character of Savitri, Narayan shows the struggle faced by many women in traditional Indian society. The period surrounding the publication of this novel was characterised by a growing awareness of women’s rights and freedom but the deep-rooted patriarchal views acted as an impediment for women to analyse individual desires against the background of traditional roles and identity. Savitri’s struggle for autonomy becomes her existential crisis fuelled by social constraints. Her husband’s dismissal of her aggravates her crisis and highlights the moral and ethical side of a marriage in which a mother has to care for her children even in an unhappy marriage.

The novel acts as an influential text in Indian feminist literature that highlights the struggle of a woman within a patriarchal framework. The existential theme is intrinsically intertwined with the feminist theme in which Savitri faces the dilemma of choosing between the traditional role of a wife and mother and the autonomy which she craves throughout the novel. Savitri’s journey can be considered a reflection of the characteristic existential dilemmas caused by the social constructs that dictate their ways that mirror the restrictions faced by women like Savitri in the domestic sphere. The dark room where Savitri retreats becomes a symbolic representation of Savitri’s psychological state. Her feelings of despair and isolation dominate when she is in the room expressing the overwhelming nature of her existence as she contemplates her feeling of being trapped in her marriage. This feeling of imprisonment generates considerable psychological turbulence within Savitri. Her existential crisis caused by rigid patriarchal norms becomes more prominent as she feels imprisoned in a marriage from which she cannot escape. The anguish that emanates from her existential crisis is even more exacerbated by her attempt to break free from the domestic sphere, her unsuccessful suicide attempt and her inability to assert herself in a society that chokes her individuality.

Narayan’s portrayal of Savitri’s psychological turbulence is evocative illustrating her thoughts allowing glimpses of her suppressed identity and simultaneously reflecting the emptiness created by her lack of autonomy. The external expectations of her family and society aggravate her identity crisis. Despite her decision to leave her husband’s house which represents her internal turmoil, she is unable to follow through with her desire to commit suicide and returns home. Her decision to return to her husband’s house is illustrative of the loneliness that accompanies her search for identity. As the story moves forward she oscillates between her role as a mother and her self. Maternal roles can supply and simultaneously restrict identity and often impose limitations and this can be seen in the Savitri’s struggle for identity who wants to live for herself and at the same time care for her children. Her struggle reaches its zenith when she thinks of her children’s well-being and the impact of her decision on her children when she is about to leave her husband’s house.

Savitri also illustrates the dynamic interaction of feminism and existential crisis in her desire for self-identity and autonomy and the expectation of society from her as a wife and mother which is true for most women in a similar context. The patriarchal structure of the society Savitri lives in not only dictates her roles and responsibilities but also her identity. Authors Rebello and Lourdsamy are of the view that intermittent explosions of Savitri's challenge are eclipsed by generalised social norms. This illustrates the harsh reality of life and society highlighting that personal freedom is not a personal choice. Therefore the interaction between autonomy and social repression reveals essential truths about a woman's existence in rigid social limitations. Narayan's *The Dark Room* serves as a symbol of oppression encapsulating the protagonist's existential crisis in her internal struggle caused by patriarchal restrictions that shape a woman's life in Indian society.

Vescovi in his exploitation of post-secular criticism is of the view that spaces such as the dark room in the novel metaphorically represent the oppressive structures of marriage and society. Darkness symbolises the absence of freedom and autonomy for Savitri. However, the darkroom has some potential for introspection and self-discovery. Savitri retreats to this room whenever her husband's irritable nature and her unsatisfactory married life become unbearable for her. It is in these moments that this dark room becomes a sanctuary for her instead of a confinement place where she engages in self-reflection and contemplates her choices she has made for herself in life. Although filled with darkness the room can illuminate her way towards self-introspection in a patriarchal society. In this aspect, the dark room is emblematic of the duality of Savitri's existence. This room which is symbolic of the absence of personal freedom and autonomy also offers her the possibility of personal reawakening.

Towards the end of the novel we see that the intersection of Savitri's personal desires and societal expectations cause in her a great stir leaving her tormented as she returns to her husband's house after spending a short time working in a temple. The existential crisis Savitri faces is deeply intertwined with her feminist struggle. Her search for meaning and identity cannot be divorced from her role as a woman in a patriarchal society. The limitations placed on her as a wife and mother lead to feelings of alienation and existential despair. In the dark room, she confronts the futility of trying to escape these roles, but she also begins to see the possibility of creating meaning for herself within the confines of her circumstances.

Savitri's experience in *The Dark Room* is a poignant commentary on the intersection of personal suffering and societal oppression. While the novel does not provide a clear resolution to her crisis, it highlights the complexities of female identity within a patriarchal framework and the struggle for autonomy in a world that does not easily allow for it. Savitri's existential crisis is intricately interwoven with her feminist struggle. Her seeking for meaning and identity cannot be separated from the condition of a woman in a patriarchal society. As a wife and mother, she is subjected to restrictions that alienate her, leading to existential despair. The dark room forces her to come to terms with the futility of escape from her roles, but also the possibility of meaning-making, failing yet succeeding to begin a life of her own. Savitri's ordeal in *The Dark Room* is a painful commentary on how personal grief meets with public tyranny. The fullness of the spirit of a woman within a patriarchal environment and the battle for independence in the lighting of our social scene are not everything the novel can discover without getting settled about the answer to her emergency.

The personal existential crisis of Savitri and the larger feminist critique of gender oppression is explored in *The Dark Room* by R.K. Narayan. Savitri's journey reveals how women's roles in society can ensnare them in cycles of self-doubt, suffering and submission. But this feminine retreat into the dark room is more than just a symbolic moment of despair, it is a challenge to reclaim the self in the face of overbearing social pressure. The novel doesn't present a simplistic feminist resolution, but it does prompt consideration of how lives lived in the throes of existential crises and gendered oppression intersect and shape one another — especially for women in the patriarchal terrain. It is partly by addressing feminist matters, such as the oppression of women in traditional Indian society, that *The Dark Room* comes into contact with those concerns. Savitri is completely constructed as a person through her relationship with her husband; her value comes from her being a part of a household, from her subservience to Ramani, and her nurturing values as a mother. Yet when Ramani fails her, she faces a stark emptiness and becomes akin to an empty shell of loss of identity. The fidelity of her husband leads her to question her entire existence: the very being of a wife and mother, for which she has come to be defined, is suddenly devalued as a consequence of the treatment undergone by her husband.

The Dark Room has often received feminist critiques based on Savitri, the character who finds herself entrapped in a rigid societal framework allowing her very few possibilities of self-expression or self-actualization. The traditional ideal of femininity insists that women be self-sacrificing and submissive to their husbands, even when it is one in which they are not genuinely satisfied if not even exploited. According to Narayan, it is in the structural inequality between men and women where one, such as Savitri, is expected to suffer in silence and has been deprived of meaningful agency or change.

It is not that Savitri's reaction to Ramani's betrayal has any empowerment in the conventional sense; it is more like an awakening in and feminist sense. Stepping out of the darkroom and her husband manifests a desperate bid to reclaim control and autonomy, albeit a temporary escape. As far as Savitri, the protagonist of the novel, is concerned, she faces the restrictions which are put on women in such positions and the ultimate question before Savitri remains whether she would ever find it possible to escape the barrenness of her existential crisis in a society that permits no doors to emancipation. While Savitri seeks some form of personal resolution, she does not return from the darkroom as an ideally realized feminist protagonist. Thus, the novel does not offer any radical or empowering solutions to the struggles that constitute her. It, instead, subtly critiques the patriarchy by portraying how the lives of women are constrained under the prevailing societal expectations and the limited roles available to them. Narayan's portrayal of suffering by Savitri, which is not overtly feminist, also makes the reader ponder on the severe structural inequalities women experience and the emotional effects of those conditions.

In *The Dark Room*, R.K. Narayan twines together the motifs of existential crisis and feminism, that reference Savitri's life events to wider philosophical and social contemplation. The inner struggle is both an individual crisis and a critique of the system's search for meaning in her life remains confined to gender. The suffering and the dark world in which Savitri resides reflect the existential anguish of the woman trapped in such a world that knows no bounds for her freedom, yet has to confront, alongside exclusion, the absurdity of existence as well as enforced patriarchal norms. Although not a straightforward feminist ending, *The Dark Room* can be referred to as an extremely constructive commentary on the condition of women in a patriarchal society and about the psychological and existential burdens that arise from systematic oppression.

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